

THE ROLE OF ONOMATOPOEIA IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Annotation: This thesis deals with the importance of onomatopoeic words in early language development and analyses the usage of onomatopoeic words and mimics in the literature of elementary level learners.

Key words: onomatopoeia, mimics, language development, word learning.

Word learning in early stages of human development has always been the centre of linguistic studies. In the early years of word-learning humans tend to associate the words with their meaning by creating the picture of that word in their mind. As soon as they learn the name of a new object they try to catch the imagery style of that object and whenever they hear those names they immediately depict the picture of those objects in their mind. In this way, children easily pick up the words that can be directly connected with objective reality. However, language doesn't only refer to the object or actions that are physically present. In this case we have to analyze some other aspects of word learning one of which is learning through onomatopoeia.

Actually, literary meaning of the word "onomatopoeia" is word-making and it represents the words that evoke the actual sound of the thing they refer to. From this point of view, onomatopoeic words are the ideal source for children to teach and to enhance their world learning process. Onomatopoeia is not only easy to remember for children as they represent real sounds but also there is an educational benefit too. Noticing and imitating sound words help children to build phonological awareness, a key aspect for speech development of early literacy. There is a gap between children's literature and any other kind of literary works. It especially concerns with the

(1st international scientific and practical conference)

characteristics to suit its intended audience. Children’s books are often shorter, optimistic rather than depressive, with dialogue rather than description, language is child-oriented.¹ According to these descriptions onomatopoeia should be prevalent in early stages of lexical development.

Onomatopoeia appear in high quantities in many children’s literature from textbooks to picture books. Onomatopoeic words that regularly come in children’s books can generally be classified into 3 large groups(*In the first table*).

Table 1

1. Animal sounds	2. Human sounds	3. Sounds that things make
Baa, bark, buzz, cheep, chirp, cock-a-doodle-doo, cuckoo, howl, meow, neigh, oink, tweet, quack	Achoo, blurt, cough, giggle, ha-ha, clap, sniff, snore, sob, whisper, yawn	Bam, bang, bubble, click, crash, flick, puff, ring, jingle, whoop, zip, sputter, twinkle

Onomatopoeic words may come in any literary form and most commons are poems, songs, tongue-twisters. In many nursery poems animal sounds are great tools to intrigue target audience. Here are some more example songs and poems that are taught to elementary learners:

*Baa, baa, black sheep, have you any wool?
 Yes sir, yes sir, three bags full.
 One for the master, one for the dame,
 And one for the little boy who lives down the lane.*(R. Kipling)

¹ Mac Dowell(1973) cited in Hunt 1998:45

*All my ducklings swimming on the lake,
Swimming on the lake, heads in the water,
Little tails up in the air! Three little kittens, they lost their mittens
And they began to cry "Oh, mother dear, we sadly fear
We've lost our mittens by" "What! Lost your mittens? you naughty kittens
Then you shall have no pie "Meow, meow, meow, my"(A. J. Relly)*

*The horn on the bus goes beep, beep, beep beep, beep, beep
Beep, beep, beep the horn on the bus goes beep, beep, beep
All 'round the town, the baby on the bus goes 'whaa whaa whaa'
Whaa whaa whaa whaa whaa whaa the baby on the bus goes
'whaa whaa whaa' All 'round the town(American folk song by V. Hills)*

*Old MacDonald had a farm ee i ee i o
And on his farm he had some cows ee i ee i oh
With a moo-moo here and a moo-moo there
Here a moo, there a moo everywhere a moo-moo
Old MacDonald had a farm ee i ee i o
Old MacDonald had a farm e i ee i o
And on his farm he had some chicks
Ee i ee i o with a cluck-cluck here
And a cluck-cluck there here a cluck, there a cluck
Everywhere a cluck-cluck.(Thomas d'Urfey)*

From the examples above, it is obvious that onomatopoeic words play an active role both in children's literature and their word learning process at early stages of their vocabulary building. These words allow children to create a more vivid picture

(1st international scientific and practical conference)

of the word in their mind as they are closely connected with the sounds of objects, animals and humans. As well as their phonological aspects which make them easy to remember is considered to be a key feature to create a musical rhythm in children's poems and songs.

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